

INTRALAMINAR CRACKING BEHAVIOUR IN CFRP LAMINATES: ULTRASONIC DETECTION AND NUMERICAL MODELLING

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SUMMARY: Matrix cracks in composite laminates are the precursor to more serious forms of damage. The results presented in this paper include ultrasonic detection of these cracks using polar backscattering and modelling of the ultrasonic interactions. The optimised transducer angle for crack detection allows detection of individual cracks and crack density to be measured. The evaluation of matrix crack density is an important tool for assessment of the structural integrity of composite laminates. Further work includes finite element simulations to evaluate the degradation of properties with increasing crack density. The strain energy release rate of the growing cracks has been predicted, and the dependence on crack length has been found. These results lead to an understanding of the accumulation of damage in composite laminates.

KEYWORDS: transverse matrix cracking, ultrasonic testing, polar backscattering, three-dimensional finite element modelling, strain energy release rate.

INTRODUCTION

Intralaminar matrix cracking is the most common damage to form when a composite laminate is loaded. It is of considerable significance for the integrity of a composite structure. These intralaminar cracks are small and hard to detect using conventional inspection techniques. Although their presence at low crack densities may be acceptable, a high density of intralaminar cracks is associated with the development of critical failure events such as delamination. The detection of these cracks and measurement of crack density is vital to ensure the structural integrity of composite laminates.

The overall aim of the present work is to provide validated constitutive relations for crack accumulation in off-axis plies under mixed mode loading. It is part of a joint research project with the University of Surrey, where experimental investigations to describe the development of the cracking are being performed. The work at Bristol focuses on two areas: ultrasonic characterisation of matrix cracks in composites and the development of finite element-based models of cracked laminates. The ultrasonic testing uses polar backscattering [1, 2]. This method allows imaging of the transverse matrix cracks embedded in the off-axis layers of the coupons. The aim is to quantify the crack density in specimens loaded in tension. Finite element analysis has also been applied to wave propagation in a composite material and the model has been validated at normal incidence. A method has been developed to model

obliquely incident waves on a cracked cross-ply laminate. The model was used to obtain the profile of maximum amplitude of the signal generated by the reflection of ultrasound on an isolated crack as the transducer is scanned along the specimen. The aim of the finite element analysis simulations is to find the optimal parameters for crack detection with polar backscattering in terms of transducer angle, size and frequency for different laminates lay-ups and crack densities. This work is ongoing. In parallel to the work on ultrasonic characterisation of cracked composites, a three-dimensional finite element analysis has been developed to simulate crack growth. It gives the strain energy release rate associated with the cracking including the mixed mode nature for off-axis laminates. Comparison of the results from the simulations with the experimental observations of the crack growth can lead to derivation of the critical conditions leading to matrix crack growth.

MATERIALS

The composite laminates investigated are carbon fibre-Epoxy (IM7/8552) of unbalanced lay-up type $(0_2/\theta_8/0_2)$ where $\theta = 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ$ and also $(0_2/90_8/0_2)$. Transverse cracks in the θ layer were introduced in the experimental programme carried out at the University of Surrey [4]. The cracks were detected via penetrant and x-ray analysis and shown to span the whole thickness and width of the central ply [4]. The crack densities in the specimens provided were all close to the critical density prior to catastrophic failure.

ULTRASONIC DETECTION OF TRANSVERSE CRACKING

Transverse cracks within composite laminates are hard to detect using normal incidence since the plane of the crack is parallel with the ultrasonic beam. Acoustic backscattering was introduced by Bar-Cohen and Crane [1] and consists of orienting the transducer at an oblique incidence angle with respect to the specimen's surface when scanning. The amount of ultrasound that is reflected back to the transducer is limited to the signals scattered by the fibres and flaws within the specimen. Vertical cracks behave like strong reflectors, generating signals of increased amplitude at the transducer. Several different incidence angles were tried, varying between 15° and 50° . An incidence angle of 20° was found to provide the most favourable imaging of the transverse cracks. This corresponds to a longitudinal wave propagating at 41.6° in the composite. Accurate positioning of the data collection gate in time was found to be crucial as it affects both the signal to noise ratio of the scan and the detection of the transverse cracks. Individual cracks can be distinguished and crack density can be assessed. Figure 1 shows the resulting scans for a $(0_2/90_4)_s$ and a $(0_2/75_4)_s$ coupon. A dense cracking pattern is detectable with oblique incidence ultrasonic testing, thus enabling a transverse matrix crack count.

Fig. 1: Polar backscattering C-scan of (150 x 20) mm coupons with transverse cracking: (a) $(0_2/90_4)_s$ and (b) $(0_2/75_4)_s$

ULTRASONIC WAVE PROPAGATION MODELLING

Normal Incidence

The interaction between ultrasonic waves and transverse cracks in composite laminates has been investigated using finite element modelling. The package used was ABAQUS Explicit version 6.4 [5]. The analyses were carried out using 2-dimensional reduced integration plane strain elements, drawn in the thickness-axial plane of the composite laminate. The ultrasonic excitation was simulated at the boundary of the model using forced displacements. The function defining the amplitude as a function of time is a windowed raised cosine as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Windowed raised cosine defining the input pulse in the time domain

The model was validated at normal incidence by comparing the longitudinal and transverse wave velocities as well as the reflection coefficient to the theoretical values [6,7]. Good agreement was found, as can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison of ultrasonic results predicted by the finite element model and theoretical values

Medium	Longitudinal Wave Velocity (m/s)		Reflection Coefficient	
	FE prediction	Classical	FE prediction	Classical
Steel	6262	6271	0.9501	0.9411
0° CFRP	2874	2876	0.5083	0.5056
90° CFRP	2877	2876	0.5081	0.5056

Oblique Incidence

The ultrasonic modelling has been extended to include modelling of an obliquely incident wave. This is achieved by imposing a time delayed forced pressure loading on consecutively excited elements. This principle of exciting consecutive elements after increasing time delays to obtain a plane wave propagating at an angle to the excitation surface's normal is used in linear phased array transducers and is referred to as beam steering. As a guideline, the distance between excitation elements should be below half a wavelength in order to avoid strong secondary signals appearing in directions other than the steering angle [8]. The

individual ultrasonic sources interfere in such a way that a monitoring point located within the material sees a plane wave passing through. The amplitude profile of the pressure load as a function of time is a windowed raised cosine shown in Figure 2. This excitation causes two modes of wave propagation: a longitudinal wave and a transverse wave, travelling in two different directions.

In order to avoid the generation of edge waves at the top corners of the model it is preferable to reduce the amplitude of excitation of the input wave on the elements nearest to the corners. This is achieved by apodisation of the input signal where the pulse on the k^{th} element in the array containing N elements in total is multiplied by a raised cosine function defined by:

$$g(k) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \cos \left(\frac{2\pi(k-1)}{N-1} \right) \right) \quad (2)$$

The desired wave propagation is obtained, without any interference from the corners of the model, as can be seen in Figure 3. The displacements are presented at a given time and in a coordinate system associated with the transverse wave. The projection of the longitudinal wave oscillations on that same coordinate system can also be seen.

Fig 3: Contour plot of displacement U_x in local coordinate system associated with a transverse wave generated in steel

The FEA model developed for wave propagation at oblique incidence was applied to a $(0_2/90_4)_s$ cross-ply laminate cracked in the central thick 90° layer. In order to represent an incident wave in water at 20° relative to the normal to the specimen, the angle of propagation of the longitudinal wave in the composite is chosen as 41.6° . The crack was modelled by removing some elements thus forming a $3 \mu\text{m}$ thick slit in the material. Figure 4 shows the wave propagation in the laminate at three different times. The first contour plot of displacements was extracted in the early stage of the wave generation. It shows the longitudinal wave propagating in the 0° layer. The second contour plot outlines the mode conversion of the longitudinal wave into a longitudinal and a transverse wave at the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface. The final contour plot presented illustrates the reflection of the longitudinal wave on the crack, while the mode converted shear wave is about to reach the crack

Fig 4: (a) Generation of oblique wave in the 0° layer (time= $0.18 \mu\text{s}$); (b) mode conversion of longitudinal wave at $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface (time= $0.36 \mu\text{s}$); (c) reflection of longitudinal wave on the crack (time= $0.56 \mu\text{s}$)

The model was used to obtain the profile of maximum amplitude of the signal generated by the reflection of ultrasound on an isolated crack as the transducer is scanned along the specimen. 10° and 20° were found to be better than 30° for crack detection as the signals generated by reflection on the crack are of higher amplitudes. The normalised results of the simulations for three different transducer angles (10° , 20° and 30°) are presented in Figure 5.

Fig 5: Simulated maximum amplitude of signal generated by reflection on an isolated crack in $(0_2/90_4)_s$ as the transducer gets closer to the crack, normalised by the maximum of the profile (at $x = 0$)

We define here the normalised amplitude as the positive peak of the reflected signal divided by the maximum of the amplitude profile. The normalised amplitude is set to 1 at $x = 0$. If we define the zone of detection of the crack as the points where the normalised amplitude is above 0.5, 20° incidence gives the narrowest region, at around 1mm. This is in good agreement with the experimental results that give a crack width of around 0.8mm on the C-scans at that angle of incidence (see Figure 1).

The aim of the finite element analysis simulations is to find the optimal parameters for crack detection with polar backscattering in terms of transducer angle, size and frequency for different laminates lay-ups and crack densities. This work is ongoing.

FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION OF MATRIX CRACK GROWTH

Matrix crack growth in CFRP laminates has been simulated using finite element analysis. The package used was ABAQUS Standard (Implicit code) version 6.4 [5]. For cross-ply laminates, the models could be drawn in two dimensions in the thickness-axial plane using generalised plane strain elements. For these 2-dimensional models, only crack growth across the whole width could be simulated. Angle-ply laminates require full 3-dimensional finite element models to simulate both mechanical properties and crack growth across the width. Linear material properties were used, but geometric non-linearity was included.

Mechanical Properties

Accumulation of matrix cracks is known to affect the mechanical properties of composite laminates. This paper presents an investigation of the cross-ply laminate $(0_2/90_4)_s$ and the angle-ply laminates $(0_2/\theta_4)_s$ where $\theta = 45^\circ$, 60° and 75° . Figures 6 and 7 show the predicted decrease of two mechanical properties with increasing crack density. Figure 6 shows the

variation of longitudinal Young's modulus and Figure 7 shows the change of in-plane Poisson's ratio.

For both properties, the variability in stiffness and Poisson's ratio with crack density is greater for the cross-ply laminate than for the angle-ply laminate. This is the expected result since a higher proportion of overall stress is carried by the 0° plies in the cross-ply laminate. For both types of laminates the variability of in-plane Poisson's ratio is far higher than the variability of stiffness. Monitoring of damage in composite laminates by monitoring transverse strains would be a far more sensitive technique than monitoring axial strains. This may be an important result for present developments in smart composite laminates.

Fig 6: Variation with crack density of predicted values of longitudinal Young's modulus

Fig 7: Variation with crack density of predicted values of in-plane Poisson's ratio

Total Energy Release Rate for Growing Cracks

The energy release rate for isolated transverse cracks in the unbalanced laminates has been investigated using three-dimensional finite element simulations. The cracks are assumed to span the entire thickness of the cracked ply. The geometry of the models takes into account the oblique end tabs used in the mechanical testing to accommodate extension-shear coupling [10]. Non-linear geometry was implemented for all the laminates, to take into account any specimen rotation in its plane. The applied strain used for the simulations was the initial cracking strain found in the experiments [4]. For the $(0_2/45_4)_s$ laminates, in which no cracking was observed for unnotched specimens, the simulations have been carried out for the propagation strain, obtained experimentally in notched specimens [4]. The strain energy release rates were found to be dependent on the elements and meshes used. Results for growing cracks across the width of the laminate are shown in Figure 8.

Fig 8: Predicted values of energy release rates for crack growth in the laminates

The results in Figure 8 represent the total energy release rate including both Mode 1 and Mode 2 contributions. The values of strain energy release rate have been calculated from the global compliance of the whole model. The variability with crack length is near zero for the cross-ply and $(0_2/45_4)_s$ laminates; this confirms previous analysis for cross-ply laminates [9]. A small increase with increasing crack length is found for the $[0_2/60_4]_s$ and $[0_2/75_4]_s$ laminates. The lowest energy release rate is found for the cross-ply laminate where the crack growth is pure Mode 1. The values for all the angle-ply laminates are all greater than those for the cross-ply laminate. It is clear that the occurrence of cracking cannot be associated with the total energy release rate; the mixture of crack opening modes must be taken into account.

Mode Mixity

The relative contribution of Modes 1 and 2 has been examined for the $(0_2/45_4)_s$ laminate. The method used is virtual crack closure [11, 12]. This is achieved using two simulations, before and after the increment of crack growth. The forces associated with the nodes to be released in the increment of crack growth are found in the first analysis. In the second analysis, after release of these nodes, the displacements of the nodes are found. Thus the virtual energy required to close the crack can be calculated, and this is considered equal to the energy required to open the crack. This method is based on the concepts of linear elastic fracture mechanics.

The incremental crack growth requires very fine meshes for accuracy. These meshes can only be attained using sub-modelling. This is a finite element analysis method which is carried out in two stages. The first global model includes the whole structure to be analysed, including the important geometric and property details of the structure, but with a coarse mesh which would not be able to reflect local stress variability. The displacements from the global model are used to load the detailed model including the area of interest, which can now be drawn using a suitable fine mesh.

The results from the $(0_2/45_4)_s$ laminate are shown in Table 2. The total value of strain energy release rate is the sum of the contributions from Mode 1 and Mode 2. The value of total strain energy release rate from this analysis is smaller than that found from the global analysis (see Figure 8). This difference is not unexpected owing to the complexity of this method and the assumptions used in the analysis which have been described above. However, the values calculated for the relative contributions of the different modes predicted in these simulations are expected to be accurate. The results show that the mode mixity throughout the crack growth across the width of the laminate is all approximately equally divided between the two modes.

Table 2: Separation of crack propagation modes for $(0_2/45_4)_s$ laminate with percentage of contribution from each mode to the total strain energy release rate

	Normalised crack length					
	0.25		0.5		0.75	
	Value J/m^2	Relative %	Value J/m^2	Relative %	Value J/m^2	Relative %
Mode 1	73.3	49.2	73.4	49.0	73.0	48.9
Mode 2	75.6	50.8	76.3	51.0	76.2	51.1
Total	148.9	100	149.7	100	149.2	100

CONCLUSIONS

Matrix cracking in composite laminates is critically related to their structural integrity. The results presented in this paper have shown that these cracks can be accurately detected using ultrasonic scanning at an oblique incidence angle of 20° . Early work on finite element simulations of wave propagation in a cross-ply laminate has confirmed that 20° is a suitable incidence angle for crack detection. Further assessment of the influence of transducer angle, frequency or size is under way. The effect of matrix cracking on the global mechanical properties of unbalanced and cross-ply laminates has been predicted using finite element analysis. The strain energy release rate associated with the crack growth has been found and the importance of mode mixity has been demonstrated. This work, combined with the experimental results in the parallel project, will lead to the provision of validated constitutive relations for crack accumulation in off-axis plies under mixed mode loading.

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